

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PROMOTION OF STUDENT-YOUTH INITIATIVES BASED ON THE GENDER APPROACH

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Promotion of Advanced Research Scholars

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Abstract: This article describes the didactic possibilities of developing the social activity of students and encouraging the initiatives of students based on the gender approach. It is also thought about the philosophical, pedagogical and psychological possibilities of encouraging the initiatives of students and young people based on the gender approach.

Keywords: student-youth, social activity, gender, gender approach, initiative, motivation, encouragement.

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The dynamics of modern social development that affect the life of every person, the emergence of new dimensions of social processes, require the study of the problem of the social role of a person in the world. At each stage of historical development, specific characteristics of social relations determine specific goals and directions of development. At a time when changes cover all spheres of social life, it is clearly expressed in human activity (culture), forms of relationships between people, and (social) changes during their activity. At the same time, in the conditions of democratization, the possibilities of self-development of boys and girls, the choice of forms and activities of social life are expanding significantly. In the past few years, in science huge attention is paid to the concept of "gender" in society, more specifically, in pedagogy and psychology, history, philosophy, sociology, linguistics and etc scientists, philosophers and pedagogue researchers are engaged in studying gender equality issues.

Conducting research on the theory and practice of developing the social activity of female students based on the gender approach in the higher educational institutions of our republic will help to form the social activity of future professionals based on the latest analytical achievements in the world.

In this regard, the research conducted on the gender approach will help to prepare well-rounded, broad-minded students on the basis of specialization, and with their help, to fully use the potential of our country's youth in order to further increase the moral and material well-being of our society. In the history of pedagogy, forming the social activity of students and youth in the society formed

the basis of the scientific directions of our scholars such as Eastern thinkers Abu Nasr Farobi, Alisher Navoi, Abdulla Avloni, Elbek (Mashriq Yunusov).

It is essential to mention that there are misconceptions and imaginations about the understanding and usage of the word gender, which is actively used today. In particular, it is observed that gender is viewed as a subject of women or a concept related to their superiority. Of course, it is misleading idea. This law clearly states that gender is a social aspect of relations between men and women in all spheres of society's life and activity, including politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education, and science. One of the most important aspects in the regulation of social relations is the presence of relevant explanations given to the concepts related to this issue.

Based on the results of the researches carried out by our republic and foreign scientists, and the analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature, it can be said that a number of scientific studies on the general culture of the individual, the formation and development of the skills of struggle against "mass culture" in students and young people conducted by several scientists, more specifically in our country pedagogues, psychologists, philosophers, sociologists such as M.L. Abdujabborova, M. Abdullayeva, Sh.A. Akramova, R.Kh. Djurayev, O. Jamoldinova, Z.K. Ismoilova, N.D. Kasimova, U.A. Kasimov, Z.M. Qurbaniyozova, M. Kuronov, U.I. Mahkamov, N.SH. Mullaboyeva, O. Musurmanova, E.M. Mukhtorov, R.M. Medetova, N. Ortikov, D.N. Roziyeva, Z.T. Saliyeva, R.G. Safarova, M.M. Tilavova, N.I. Khalilova, Sh.T. Khalilova, B.Kh. Khodjayev, G.B. Shoumarov, B. Sh. Shermukhammadov, Kh.M. Tojiboyeva carried out researches on the promotion of student-youth initiatives based on the gender approach.

Issues of raising personal culture, mass culture, gender socialization from CIS scientists N. Andreyeva, V.A. Bachinin, Sh. Bern, O.S. Bogdanova, Y.A. Gapova, Y.S. Gritsenko, Z.A. Zorina, Y.A. Zdravomislova, Y.P. Ilin, A. V. Kirilina, A. Kletsin, I. S. Kon, R. Connell, V. T. Kondrashenko, I. V. Kostikova, A. V. Kukarkin, D. Lorber, D. V. Olshansky, G. G. Solovyova, K. West, etc. researched and scientific-methodical bases were developed.

Pedagogical experiences show that gender issues catch interest of everyone - today's students, tomorrow's parents and teachers, or professionals, regardless of profession or field, we all need knowledge based on a gender perspective. In particular, in the educational process, educators began to take into account in depth the gender identity (characteristics) of learners.

Education based on a gender approach is the psychological gender of a person, that is, the achievement of a certain level of sexual self-awareness and sexual identification, the real occupation of the male or female role. The subject of

the field of gender studies is the socialization of individuals, which consists in the formation of gender identity and the development of gender roles.

Conducting research on the theory and practice of developing the social activity of students and young people based on the gender approach in higher educational institutions of our republic will help to form the social activity of future specialists based on new analytical achievements.

In this article, we are inclined to think about encouraging student initiatives. However, before starting to cover this topic, we found it necessary to give the definition of these concepts.

Initiative (Latin Initiare-start) - initiative in promoting and implementing any new idea, solving any problem, giving internal impetus to new forms of activity. In the pedagogical dictionary, initiative is interpreted as a personal characteristic illustrated by the ability and inclination to active and independent actions.

Motivation is the activity of directing a person's interest, desires and aspirations. It is a combination of intellectual, physiological and mental processes that determine how persistently a person acts in certain situations and in which direction his energy is concentrated.

Encouragement is the process of using specific stimuli for the benefit of a person, as well as influence, motivation, external influence on certain actions.

According to the analysis of the scientific literature of Western countries and the results of a number of studies, philosophical, sociological and psychological-pedagogical concepts related to the development and professional formation of a person (B.G.Ananav, L.Vygotsky, Y.Klimov, S.L.Rubinstein, V.A.Slastenin) studied in the researches of pedagogues, psychologists and philosophers.

In particular, personality development includes: socially important personality qualities - social activity, attention to self-awareness in activities, responsibility, independence, initiative. The formation of initiative includes activities organized by young people together with adults, turning them into self-activation. Initiative is considered as an important condition of human development and the result of personal education. The content of educational activities aimed at forming initiative in the educational process is to help the learner to develop his personality through creative activity. In this case, the teacher pays attention to the interests, needs, and intellectual abilities of the students. A person's formed need for initiative, independent action, social activity, entrepreneurial ability and activity: forms personal quality or initiative.

Long-term traditions, culture, customs, national holidays, and rich ancient heritage of our people have a special place and importance in the development of elements of social activity and initiative in students and young people according to our national values. On the basis of formation and strengthening of national pride

among students, special importance has been given to increase their social activities and initiatives. Mental intelligence, mental and spiritual maturity, honesty, kindness are the main qualities of enlightened and spiritual people. Forming these qualities in our youth is an important task today. In the current process of globalization, only young people who are disciplined, responsible, patient, pious, conscientious, faithful, tolerant, humanitarian, socially active and possessing such noble qualities will have all the comforts necessary for living. The extent to which a person can appreciate the value of self-awareness, the democratic development process of social development, and the ability to serve the society directly depends on his actions. All this is related to the social activity and initiative of a person. Social activation of students and young people is understood as the conscious and independent participation of their representatives in social processes, and when necessary, they strive to help change social relations without external pressure. Responsibility is one of the important indicators that determine the maturity of a person in the process of socialization. Another direction of socialization related to the sense of responsibility is the goals and ideals formed in the individual. They ensure that a person is ready to predict the future, imagine tomorrow, and implement long-term and short-term plans. These goals are always characterized by their awareness and dependence on the real capabilities of a person. In a certain sense, ideals also play an essential role in their formation and settling in the mind.

The main form of social activity is the responsible performance of duties and tasks, which can become an initiative under favorable conditions. Activities, including work, education, and play a leading role in the composition of the qualities of a socially active person. For example, a participant learns to obey general requirements in a game. He understands the meaning of game actions. In the process of games, initiative is formed.

In this regard, development of students' personal potential and increase of their creative initiative and social activity should be carried out in two ways:

- in the educational process;
- outside the educational process.

Possibilities of encouraging the initiatives of students and youth based on the gender approach, the interaction between students and teachers should be based on the following conditions:

- 1) to demonstrate to students the importance of educational activities for the teaching team;
- 2) to ensure the voluntary visit of professors and teachers at events (personal contribution ensures interest in the result of the preparatory process);

3) control of preparation for the event: freedom to creativity of students and the scope of the content of the event, the balance between the goals and tasks of higher educational activity;

4) building and coordinating the "vertical" interaction of students: joint activities of students from the 1st to the 4th year within the framework of higher education;

5) seamless integration of various specialists into student activities (developing strategic thinking, increasing competitiveness and professional mobility, mastering effective communication and leadership models);

6) use of various mechanisms to create motivation for participation in extracurricular activities;

7) formation of students-youth's skills for social activity in society (in the activities of the Youth Union, environmental protection actions, initiative actions in showing kindness, charity houses, orphanages, nursing homes, environmental movement, local history, participation in cultural movements, initiative activities, trade unions in the activities of primary organizations, women's and their committees in the activities of primary organizations, activities of religious committees, society of persons with disabilities (committee using the experience of active people in the society in participating in the activities of the disabled, deaf and dumb, national centers);

8) formation of the most mobile and open social groups of students according to social and gender indicators.

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